

Searching for the Rotational Spectrum of CH₂OH

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ABSTRACT

Hydroxymethyl radical (CH_2OH) is a radical fragment of methanol, and an important molecule in understanding astrochemistry. Its precursor is abundant, its isomer has already been detected towards B1-b, and it is a key intermediate in the production of more complex hydrocarbons, but its rotational spectrum is not yet known. Identification of this fragment and its isomer CH_3O in spectral data could improve our understanding of the development of chemical complexity in space, and could also be used to constrain models of desorption and branching ratios of methanol photodissociation. We sought to measure the rotational spectrum of CH_2OH to open the door for its observation in space. Spectrum predictions were made based on infrared experiments by Roberts et al., and a millimeter-wave absorption cell, operating in the 70–500 GHz range was used to search for the rotational spectrum of CH_2OH . A number of candidate lines were found, but none could be clearly identified as belonging to CH_2OH . Previously unmeasured lines of CH_3O were also determined. Future work will involve increasing the production efficiency of CH_2OH and searching for its *b*-type spectrum.

1. Introduction

The chemistry of star- and planet-forming regions is rich and diverse. Molecules such as glycoaldehyde, detected in the Class 0 protostellar binary IRAS 16293-2422 (Jørgensen et al. 2012), as well as isopropyl cyanide and the nucleobase intermediate E-cyanomethanimine, both of which were detected toward the star-forming region Sagittarius B2(N) (Belloche et al. 2014; Zaleski et al. 2013), are all examples of the increase in chemical complexity observed in such regions. Investigating 1) the origin of such complex chemistry, 2) where it

appears, and 3) at which stage of protostellar evolution it occurs, could provide clues as to the origins of chemical complexity in the solar system, and perhaps provide a sense of how unique the presence of prebiotic molecules was on the young Earth.

An important species in understanding the development of chemistry in space is methanol (CH_3OH). One of the most abundant organic molecules in star-forming regions, methanol has been detected in the gas phase in fractional abundances (with respect to H_2) of 10^{-7} – 10^{-6} (e.g. Öberg et al. 2009a; Maret et al. 2005) and in ices in abundances of 10^{-6} – 10^{-5} (Öberg et al. 2011). Methanol is typically the most abundant molecular species of its size present in hot cores and corinos (Herbst & van Dishoeck 2009). In colder regions, methanol is thought to form and be frozen out onto the surfaces of icy grains: it has been observed in the solid phase in 16 sources by Bottinelli et al. (2010), and Watanabe & Kouchi (2002) demonstrated methanol production via grain surface hydrogenation of CO on H_2O -CO ice. Moreover, since it is thought to initially form in the cold initial phase of the life of a protostar (Herbst & van Dishoeck 2009), methanol’s relative abundance and early presence makes it an excellent candidate species in helping to determine the chemistry that follows after.

In regions around a protostar, UV photons created by the interaction of cosmic rays with H_2 will process species to form radicals, which then recombine to form larger species. Photodissociation of gas-phase methanol with photons near the energies of Lyman- α produces formaldehyde (H_2CO), methoxy radical (CH_3O), and hydroxymethyl radical (CH_2OH) in an approximate ratio of $\text{H}_2\text{CO}:\text{CH}_3\text{O}:\text{CH}_2\text{OH} = 20:5:3$ (Lucas et al. 2015). These branching ratios are wavelength-dependent, but the overall trend is that photodissociation of gas-phase methanol favors the production of CH_3O over CH_2OH . On the surfaces of icy grains, methanol photodissociation is thought to favor the production of CH_2OH , but this branching ratio is not known to high precision (Öberg et al. 2009b).

The methoxy and hydroxymethyl radicals can then react to form products such as formic acid (HCOOH), ethylene glycol ($(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2$), and others (Öberg et al. 2009b; Garrod et al. 2008). These reactions can take place in appreciable amounts due to the higher probability of collision: the molecules are constrained to the surface of the ice, and not freely moving in 3D space. However, the radicals can also be ejected into the gas phase, for example by way of the leftover energy of an absorbed photon that caused a photodissociation event.

Observations of the gas-phase $\text{CH}_2\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{O}$ ratio can test the level of this photoprocessing of ices in space. Between these two methanol fragments, CH_2OH is the more stable isomer (Saebø et al. 1983) and is the preferred radical to form on the surface of methanol ices, but in the gas phase, photodissociation favors the production of CH_3O . Therefore, assuming the photodesorption of radicals off of the surfaces of icy grains preserves the branching ratio found there, a high $\text{CH}_2\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{O}$ ratio would imply a large contribution of radicals from ice photoprocessing and desorption, while a low ratio would identify gas-phase photodissociation as the primary source of reactive methanol fragments. It is worth noting, however, that the lack of isomeric selectivity in photodesorption of methanol fragments is an assumption that remains to be tested. The rotational spectrum of CH_3O has been experimentally measured up to ~ 200 GHz by Endo et al. (1984), so all that remains to be determined is the rotational spectrum of CH_2OH before this ratio can be directly observed.

The observation of CH_2OH and the determination of the $\text{CH}_2\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{O}$ ratio also have other applications. In our own solar system, comets, leftovers from the protoplanetary disk around the young Sun, and their chemistry are studied to better understand the chemistry of the young solar system and how it developed. Rodgers & Charnley (2005) have discussed how the $\text{CH}_2\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{O}$ ratio can be used to determine the prevalence of suprathermal reactions with fast H atoms in cometary comae.

Molecules in very dense and dusty regions of the interstellar medium are mainly observed via their rotational spectra in emission. Laboratory measurements can therefore provide astronomers with the information needed to discover new astronomical species. Endo et al. (1984) produced CH_3O by reacting CH_3OH with F atoms obtained by the application of a 2450 MHz discharge to an equal base pressure (7 mTorr) of CF_4 in an absorption cell 1 m long and with an outer diameter of 10 cm. The measurement of the rotational lines of CH_3O allowed Cernicharo et al. (2012) to detect methoxy radical in B1b, a dense core and the most prominent core in Barnard 1 (B1), which lies in the Perseus molecular cloud (see Walawender et al. 2005; Enoch et al. 2006). Cernicharo et al. made their detection using the IRAM 30 m telescope, and derived a methoxy temperature of $T \simeq 10 \pm 3$ K.

Much theoretical study has also been made of CH_2OH , which is an asymmetric top molecule and can be thought of as planar with highly anharmonic vibrations (see Bruna & Grein 1998; Chen & Davidson 2001; Marenich & Boggs 2003). Rettrup et al. (1988) calculated the dipole moment projections of CH_2OH along arbitrary axes, which, when projected onto the principal molecular axes (see Figure 1), yield values of $\mu_a \sim -0.07$ D (Debye), $\mu_b \sim -1.40$ D, and $\mu_c \sim -0.21$ D (see Appendix A). Experimental work has also been done: Roberts et al. (2013) carried out measurements of the infrared spectrum of CH_2OH generated in a discharge. Two sets of precursors, CH_3OH in a 70% neon, 30% helium (Ne70) mixture, and CH_3OH in Ne70 doped with Cl_2 to promote cleavage of a C–H bond. They obtained experimental values for the B and C rotational constants (the quoted value of A was theoretical, not experimentally determined). (The rotational constants are inversely proportional to the moment of inertia along each principle axis, and dictate the energy levels of the molecule: they appear in the Hamiltonian of a freely rotating molecule, $\hat{H} = A\hat{J}_a^2 + B\hat{J}_b^2 + C\hat{J}_c^2$.)

We report a search for the rotational spectrum of the hydroxymethyl radical CH_2OH , in order to allow observation of the $\text{CH}_2\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{O}$ ratio in astronomical sources. We predicted the spectrum of CH_2OH using the rotational constants determined by Roberts et al., produced radicals in a glass absorption cell, optimized for the production of CH_2OH by optimizing CH_3O production, and scanned using a magnetic field to single out the transitions of radical species.

2. Experimental

2.1. Instrument

In the relatively high-pressure and temperature environments achievable the spectrometer used in this project, the short timescales on which these reactive molecules exist necessitate their constant production. The general strategy involves a constant flow of precursor gas through a cylindrical glass cell, which reacts due to a constantly applied glow discharge—similar to the discharge in a neon light.

A block diagram of the experiment is shown in Figure 2. The glass chamber is surrounded on the exterior by tubing through which liquid nitrogen was pumped to control the temperature of the cell. Precursor gases were constantly flowed through the cell at fixed rates controlled by mass flow controllers. These gases encountered a stable 1000 V glow discharge across two electrodes at opposite ends of the cell. The constant discharge brings about an approximate equilibrium in the production of the desired species. To stabilize the discharge, inert gases (usually argon) were pumped in along with the precursors.

Microwave radiation is produced by a Gunn oscillator, which may or may not pass into a multiplier depending on the frequency range being scanned. This then passes into a horn and through a grid polarizer oriented at a 45° angle outside the cell. The plane-polarized

radiation passes through the gas in the cell and is absorbed at specific wavelengths. A dihedral mirror at the opposite end of the cell reflects the beam and rotates the radiation's plane of polarization by 90° , and upon exiting the cell it reflects off of the polarizer and into the detector.

To ensure that the radiation is being produced at the desired frequency, the Gunn oscillator is hooked into a phase-lock loop, which applies corrections to the voltage ultimately according to an 850 MHz phase-locked source. Synthesizers, multipliers, and other elements match the Gunn frequency to the phase-locked source, and produce the desired output frequency. The total frequency range of the experiment is 70–500 GHz.

Frequency modulation is applied to the radiation in order to improve signal-to-noise, and isolate the signal from any stray photons the detector receives. It should be noted that introducing frequency modulation requires collecting the first derivative of the true absorption signal, so another derivative is taken of the signal before being written to disk and displayed for clarity in line position. Therefore, lines in the spectra below will not appear as single “inverted-peak” absorption features, but the second derivative of this shape.

The detector, a liquid helium cooled InSb bolometer, outputs signal to a lock-in amplifier, which also receives output from the frequency modulation generator. The signal is passed through an analog-to-digital convertor and collected on a computer, which controls the sweeping of the frequency over a given range. The phase-lock loop is only able to ensure the correct output frequency over a short range, so multiple scans are required to cover a decently sized search window.

In order to identify absorption lines belonging to radical species, a longitudinal magnetic field was created with a solenoid wrapped around the outside of the chamber. The coupling of the unpaired electron in radicals with the magnetic field changes the energy

level structure, so consecutive scans of the same frequency range with and without an applied magnetic field reveal lines of radical species.

More details can be found in McCarthy et al. (1995), in which a very similar instrument setup to this experiment, including much of the same equipment, was used.

2.2. Strategy

The general strategy for finding CH_2OH began with predicting the spectrum from the rotational constants found by Roberts et al. (2013). Herb Pickett’s SPCAT code (described in Pickett 1991), which diagonalizes the matrix of the Hamiltonian for each angular momentum value to find the energy levels, was used to calculate a spectrum prediction.

Optimal production of CH_2OH was achieved by repeated measurements taken in differing conditions, set by the precursor(s) and buffer gas flow rates, temperature, and discharge current. Without the ability to optimize production while measuring lines of CH_2OH , we chose to optimize for the production of its isomer, CH_3O . We operated on the assumption that the presence of CH_3O indicated the presence of CH_2OH in roughly equal amounts, especially because CH_2OH is the more stable isomer by $\sim 5 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ (Saebø et al. 1983). (The production of these radicals operated by a different mechanism as gas-phase methanol photodissociation, so the branching ratios favoring CH_3O production described above do not apply.) Initial attempts to produce CH_2OH were carried out using methane and oxygen, since Vranckx et al. (2008) indicated that both methoxy and hydroxymethyl were produced in the same reaction, which provided support for our assumption. However, methoxy was not found with these precursors, and we instead used methanol as a precursor.

Methanol was introduced to the cell by placing it in a round bottom flask, and controlling the flow of methanol vapor into the cell with a mass flow controller. The flask

was placed in a warm water bath to raise the partial pressure of methanol in the source flask. The cell was cooled to -50°C to avoid freezing the methanol to the sides of the chamber while still maintaining low pressure and safe conditions to operate the discharge. Argon gas was also flowed through the cell to stabilize the discharge, which minimized noise due to inhomogeneity inside the cell.

An expected drawback to using methanol as a precursor was the contamination of the background with several strong transitions. The expected intensity of the hydroxymethyl radical transitions for which we searched is such that they are barely discernible from the noise, and overlap of the desired transitions by the much stronger methanol lines makes it much more difficult to identify the desired lines. This problem was alleviated with the use of magnetic scans as described above.

3. Results

3.1. Optimization on CH_3O

Methoxy radical was first detected from three transitions measured at 198.56033 GHz with $(J' K'_a K'_c F'_1 F' \leftarrow J'' K''_a K''_c F''_1 F'') = (4\ 0\ 0\ 8\ 4 \leftarrow 3\ 0\ 1\ 8\ 3)$, 198.56342 GHz $(4\ 0\ 1\ 8\ 4 \leftarrow 3\ 0\ 0\ 8\ 3)$, and 198.56896 GHz $(4\ 0\ 1\ 12\ 3 \leftarrow 3\ 0\ 0\ 12\ 2)$ by Endo et al. (1984), where J , K_a , K_c , F_1 , and F are the quantum numbers corresponding to the angular momentum, the projection of the angular momentum onto the a and c inertial axes, and the hyperfine structure, respectively, the prime states represent the upper level, and the doubly primed states represent the lower level. The spectra showing the unambiguous detection of CH_3O is shown in Figure 3. The signal collected from two consecutive scans without and with an applied magnetic field are shown, as well as the subtraction of the latter from the former, in which only lines belonging to magnetically active species (i.e., radicals) should

appear. One non-magnetic line appears in these spectra, which remains unidentified and is most likely due to contamination within the cell. The discharge was then turned off, and the methoxy lines disappeared, confirming its detection.

Optimal production conditions for CH_3O occurred at a cell temperature of $-50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, partial pressures of 15 mTorr Ar and 12 mTorr CH_3OH , and a 1 kV, 20 mA discharge. In the Roberts et al. experiment, hydroxymethyl radicals were jet-cooled in supersonic expansion, so there is no direct comparison to their production conditions. One would expect that a relatively low discharge current would be sufficient when using methanol as a precursor, since the desired product is formed upon the breaking of only one C–H bond. Given how generally unpredictable and imprecise the discharge method is, its occasional variation in signal over the timescale of a few hours, and the contamination within the cell from other experiments, it is not unexpected that optimal conditions will not be shared between different discharge instruments. The best strategy for finding optimal conditions is therefore most likely to do so only with the instrument being used in mind.

Two previously unmeasured lines of CH_3O were also detected (see Figure 4)—the rotational spectrum has only been measured up to ~ 200 GHz by Endo et al. (1984). The newly measured lines in this experiment are both 1.3 MHz higher than predicted in the JPL catalogue (Pickett et al. 1998). When further determining the rotational spectrum of CH_3O , it is of interest to refine predictions at lower frequency, since the deviations from prediction will increase as frequency increases. As of yet, CH_3O has only been detected in a “cold” source, Cernicharo et al. (2012) having made their observations in the 82.5–117.5 GHz range. However, searches for CH_3O in hotter sources and/or higher frequency bands will eventually require better precision in those ranges.

Assignment of these two lines to CH_3O was also helpful in the search for CH_2OH . Due to the nature of the experiment, different Gunn oscillators were needed to reach different

frequency bands—the entire 70–500 GHz range was not continuously accessible. The ability to optimize and continue to confirm production of CH₃O in between searches for lines of CH₂OH without undergoing the time-consuming and potentially problematic process of changing Gunn oscillators was ideal. These previously unmeasured lines happened to fall near enough to a search range for CH₂OH so that changing the Gunn oscillator was not necessary to access either range.

3.2. Search for CH₂OH

A sample of magnetic surveys for hydroxymethyl is presented in Figure 5. Several features in the magnetic scans appeared due to incomplete subtraction, but four candidate lines at ~ 222.887 GHz, ~ 222.895 GHz, ~ 277.675 GHz, and ~ 277.678 GHz were identified from these magnetic surveys that were confirmed not to be due to this effect (see Figure 6). These candidates were confirmed to be magnetic lines; however, their locations differ substantially from the SPCAT prediction, and could possibly be due to the discharge producing magnetically active species from contamination present in the cell. We were therefore unable to unambiguously assign any lines to CH₂OH.

4. Discussion and Prospects

All searches for CH₂OH in this experiment have been for transitions in the *a*-type spectrum. An *a*-type transition is a transition for which $\Delta K_a = 0$ ($\pm 2, \pm 4, \dots$) and $\Delta K_c = \pm 1$ ($\pm 3, \pm 5, \dots$). After carrying out scans of CH₃O and searches for CH₂OH, it is unlikely that the *a*-type spectrum will be detectable in current conditions.

The projection of the dipole moment along the *a*-axis of CH₂OH is not strong enough compared to that of CH₃O. Since the line intensities are proportional to the square

of the dipole moment, a decrease in the dipole moment will have a large effect on the intensities. Normalized to an integration time of ~ 1500 s, 10 mV sensitivity, and 5V of signal from the bolometer, the (peak-to-peak) signal we see for CH_3O is ≈ 0.35 , and the noise is at $N \sim 0.08$. Under the assumption that CH_2OH and CH_3O are being produced in approximately equal amounts, the intensity of the a -type spectrum of CH_2OH can be roughly estimated by

$$S(\text{CH}_2\text{OH}) \approx S(\text{CH}_3\text{O}) \left(\frac{\mu_a(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})}{\mu_a(\text{CH}_3\text{O})} \right)^2.$$

From an examination of the noise, the minimum allowable peak-to-peak signal for detecting CH_2OH is $\min(S(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})) \sim 0.19$. For this to be achieved, the dipole moment projected on the A inertial axis of CH_2OH must satisfy

$$(0.19) \lesssim (0.35) \left(\frac{\mu_a(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})}{(2.12)} \right)^2$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_a(\text{CH}_2\text{OH}) \gtrsim 1.6.$$

Since the actual value of $\mu_A(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})$ is ~ 0.07 D as calculated by Rettrup et al. (1988), Carl Gottlieb, and myself (see Appendix A), we do not expect to see the a -type spectrum of CH_2OH in current observing conditions. Initial searches for CH_2OH transitions were for a -type transitions, since to first order these depend only on the values of B and C , which are known much better than the theoretical value for A given by Roberts et al. (2013). The b -type lines, which depend to first order on A and C , thus have much higher uncertainties in frequency. It was not known a priori what level of sensitivity was achievable, so initial searches were done for transitions with the lowest frequency uncertainty.

There are other possibilities as to why CH_2OH has not been detected yet. The first is that the production efficiency of CH_2OH is too low. This is probably not the case, because as was explained earlier, the presence of CH_3O should imply the presence of CH_2OH due to the relative stabilities and formation pathways. This could be dealt with by attempting to

further optimize conditions to strengthen the CH_3O signal. Despite the evidence to support this assumption, it is also possible that CH_3O production does not imply a similar amount of CH_2OH production.

One way to increase CH_2OH production would be to introduce Cl_2 , since its presence selectively removes a hydrogen from carbon instead of oxygen to form HCl . Roberts et al. (2013) used this method and saw an increase in CH_2OH by a factor of two, so while it may not solve the *a*-type spectrum problem, it could render CH_2OH lines much more visible in the magnetic surveys.

5. Conclusions

This project was dedicated to the determination of the rotational spectrum of CH_2OH . Based on infrared data, line predictions were made, but with high uncertainty. Optimized production of CH_3O allowed the determination of two of its previously unmeasured transitions, which fell ~ 1.3 MHz higher than predictions. This means that laboratory measurement of higher-frequency lines of CH_3O are necessary before observations of them can be made by astronomers. Four candidate lines of the rotational spectrum of CH_2OH were found, but lines unambiguously corresponding to CH_2OH have yet to be located. This project will continue by both attempting increase the production efficiency of CH_2OH (possibly by introducing Cl_2 doping) and searching for more intense *b*-type transitions. Eventual determination of the rotational constants and microwave spectrum of hydroxymethyl will then open the door for its astronomical detection.

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A. Reproduction of ground-state dipole moments of CH₂OH

Rettrup et al. (1988) gave coordinate values for each atom in CH₂OH in terms of arbitrary axes, labeled x , y , and z (see Table 1). These coordinates were used, along with each atomic mass, to calculate the center of mass of the molecule and the principal axis coordinates of each atom by Carl Gottlieb. Then, using the dipole moments calculated by Rettrup et al. along the arbitrary axes (see Table 3), I reprojected the dipole moments along the a , b , and c axes (Table 4). There is no way to verify that the geometry used by Rettrup et al. is the same geometry adopted by Roberts et al. and shown in Figure 1, but the two adopt similar conformations with the hydrogens bonded to carbon not sharing a plane with the C–O bond. Therefore it is reasonable to assume that the derived dipole moment projections provide a close enough estimate to determine that the a -type spectrum was not observable.

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Fig. 1.— Three-dimensional model of CH₂OH from Roberts et al. (2013), with the highest-occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and principal axes drawn.

Fig. 2.— Block diagram of the experiment. Note that optimal CH₃O production occurred at a 20 mA discharge, not at 300 mA.

Fig. 3.— a) Observed lines of CH_3O with no applied magnetic field. b) Application of an external magnetic field shifts the lines of the radical CH_3O , but leaves the unidentified line (“u-line”) unchanged. c) Subtraction of panel b signal from panel a signal. d) Spectrum of same region with discharge turned off. The u-line at ~ 198.566 GHz appears throughout.

Fig. 4.— Experimental measurements of the two detected CH_3O lines, which differ from predictions by ~ 1.3 MHz. Signal shown is magnetic field OFF-ON to isolate the signal of the radical from background lines.

Fig. 5.— Magnetic surveys for CH_2OH . Different colors denote different scans. To constitute a detection of a radical species, the line should appear in the bottom panel with approximately the same intensity as the top panel. Several features present in OFF–ON panel are due to incomplete subtraction, confirmed candidate lines appear in Figure 6.

Fig. 6.— Four CH_2OH candidate lines. In order to verify that features were not due to incomplete subtraction, a higher resolution scan was taken of the lines in the left panel, which appears here. Signal shown is magnetic field OFF-ON to isolate the signal of the radical from background lines.

Table 1. Hydroxymethyl atom positions in arbitrary (x, y, z) coordinate system

Atom	x (a_0)	y (a_0)	z (a_0)
C	0	0	0
O	1.35745	0	0
H1	-0.504428	-0.796273	-0.523054
H2	-0.419645	0.98817	-0.026512
H	1.6857	-0.883857	0

References. — Rettrup et al. 1988

Note. — Atoms H1 and H2 are the hydrogens attached to the carbon, and H is the hydrogen on oxygen. The unit a_0 denotes the Bohr radius.

Table 2. Hydroxymethyl atom positions in principal axis (a, b, c) coordinate system

Atom	a (a_0)	b (a_0)	c (a_0)
C	-0.723242	-0.018665	0.0512888
O	0.629815	0.0640034	-0.0200129
H1	-1.19124	-0.930324	-0.283286
H2	-1.21162	0.918266	-0.140882
H	1.01875	-0.781481	0.1311

References. — Rettrup et al. 1988, Carl Gottlieb

Note. — Atoms H1 and H2 are the hydrogens attached to the carbon, and H is the hydrogen on oxygen.

Table 3. Dipole moment and projections along arbitrary axes of CH₂OH

μ_{tot}	μ_x	μ_y	μ_z
	(D)	(D)	(D)
1.43	-0.14	-1.33	-0.48

References. — Rettrup et al.
1988

Note. — 1 Debye is equal to
 $1/299\,792\,498 \times 10^{-21}$ C·m.

Table 4. Dipole moment and projections along principal molecular axes of CH₂OH

μ_{tot}	μ_a	μ_b	μ_c
	(D)	(D)	(D)
1.42	-0.07	-1.40	-0.21